

RESEARCH ON REFLECTION OF PACKAGING MATERIALS**Mansurov Mukhtorjon Toxirjonovich***Namangan Engineering Construction Institute Namangan,
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Abstract. The reflectivity (reflectance) of various materials was studied as the possibility of polarization of light. The design of the stand and the method of quantitative assessment of the fraction of polarized light reflected from foil and polymer films, which is necessary for the pleochroism effect used in protective printing (packaging), have been developed.

Key words: pleochroism, polymer films, illumination, polarization, reflection.

The annealing of polymer films under directed polarized light is shown. A wide range of colors can be obtained by assembling a multi-layer bag consisting of polyethylene, polyvinyl chloride, polystyrene films [1]. The study of the light reflection effect was carried out using two polarizing screens or a liquid crystal monitor as a source of polarized light [2]. The use of double-polarized film leads to high material costs, which cannot be used in the production of consumer goods packaging materials.

The study of the reflection of various metallic and non-metallic materials used in packaging production, because the reflected light is polarized, and its use allows

the design of brightly colored elements that protect the packaging from counterfeiting [4] and attract the attention of buyers is enough.

Titanium foil and polycarbonate sheet with a thickness of 3 ± 0.2 mm were used to reflect the light. A DT-1308 luxmeter was used to measure the intensity of the illuminated light. The light source is a YN0906 II LED lamp with a color temperature of 5500 K.

Figure 1. Stand reflectance (reflected light) to measure intensity:

1 - Hinge; 2 - reflective material; 3 - LED lamp; 4 - light meter

The device is assembled to measure the angular characteristics of the reflected beam.

(Fig. 1) The distance between the light source and the lux meter is 60 cm in a straight line, the length of the sail on which the instruments are installed is 30 cm, the light source is installed at an angle of 45 degrees.

Discussion of results. It is known that light reflected from a transparent dielectric is partially polarized according to Brewster's law, the angle between the light passing through a transparent dielectric material and the polarized light reflected from its surface must be equal to 90 degrees. The tangent of the angle

of light incidence at which its polarization is maximum is equal to the refractive index of the material [3].

The first object to study the refraction of light was glass, and when light is reflected from the glass, the polarization of light is not determined. Therefore, it is impossible to use metal sheet glass and similar inorganic materials as a medium for obtaining polarized light.

Polarization of light during refraction of light on non-dielectric titanium foil was determined. Polarization when reflecting light with titanium foil is due to the presence of an oxide film on its surface, which is a transparent dielectric.

The graph of the dependence of light intensity on the angle of light reflection of titanium foil and polycarbonate is shown in the figure. (Fig. 2) with the help of a 70-diode light source, maximum reflection effect is achieved in wide viewing angles under experimental conditions. 30,60 degrees for titanium foil and 50,70 degrees for polycarbonate plate. When the point light source works, the angular coordinate of the maximum intensity of light reflected from the titanium foil is 40,50 degrees, and for the polycarbonate plate it is 45,55 degrees.

Based on the obtained data, a table of light reflection coefficients for various materials was compiled. (table. 1) It can be seen that the light reflection of titanium foil is 1.5 times higher than that of polycarbonate with the same polarization ratio. (Fig. 3)

Figure 2.
Reflecting with
polycarbonate
titanium foil:
titanium foil.

The evaluation of light polarization and the possibility of obtaining the effect of beam deflection at this stage was carried out by the visual [2] method, using multilayer packages of polyethylene and polyvinyl chloride films covered with a single polarizing film, which served as an analyzer. The most saturated and pure colors were obtained in the range from 30 to 60 degrees for all the presented samples, except for the mirror.

From 0 to 30 degrees and from 60 to 90 degrees, the effect of light dimming does not give the desired effect on color saturation.

Mirror angle, degree.

Figure 3. Fraction of polarized light in the mirror:

1 - polycarbonate sheet; 2 - titanium foil

Table 1 Optical characteristics of the mirror

Characteristics	Reflective material		
	Mirror	titanium foil	polycarbonate sheet
Reflection coefficient	0,94	0,48	0,26
Maximum fraction of light polarizer, %	0	86	88

Summary.

The reflectivity of various metallic and non-metallic materials used in packaging production has been studied. The polarization of light reflected from metal and polycarbonate foils, used in the production of flexible packaging bags for consumer goods, can be used in security printing in combination with the pleochroism effect of the films. The technologies and machines mentioned above are designed to print the necessary information on flat and smooth materials. Trademarks and other information on bubble wraps have not been considered. In order to solve this problem, the scientists of the "Technological machines and equipment" department of the Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute executed an economic agreement on this issue and made a device that performs this task.

The created device differs in that it is much simpler and cheaper than existing machines. Currently, scientific research is being conducted in this direction, and a

new type of paint apparatus has been invented and an application for a patent has been filed.

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